

TAXINOMISIS: A cloud – based platform for risk profiling and patient specific management of the carotid artery disease

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Abstract – Carotid Artery Disease is a complex multi-disciplinary medical condition causing strokes and several other disfunctions to individuals. Within this work, a cloud - based platform is proposed for clinicians and medical doctors that provides a comprehensive risk assessment tool for carotid artery disease. It includes three modeling levels: baseline data-driven risk assessment, blood flow simulations and plaque progression modeling. The proposed models, which have been validated through a wide set of studies within the TAXINOMISIS project, are delivered to the end users through an easy-to-use cloud platform. The architecture and the deployment of this platform includes interfaces for handling the electronic patient record, the 3D arterial reconstruction, blood flow simulations and risk assessment reporting. TAXINOMISIS, compared with both similar software approaches and with the current clinical workflow, assists clinicians to treat patients more effectively and more accurately by providing innovative and validated tools.

Keywords—machine learning models, carotid artery disease, risk profile, plaque evolution model, blood simulation model

I. INTRODUCTION

When plaque builds up in the carotid arteries, which carry blood to the brain, the arteries become narrowed or obstructed, a condition known as carotid artery disease[1]. The risk of stroke may rise as a result of the brain receiving insufficient oxygen and nutrients. Neck pain, faintness, and momentary loss of vision or speech are some of the signs of carotid artery disease. Smoking, hypertension, and excessive cholesterol are all risk factors for the condition. Because it is a main cause of stroke, which can lead to disability or death, this condition has a large impact on the society. In addition, carotid artery disease patients' treatment and care expenses may strain healthcare infrastructure.

Clinicians have long been interested in the risk profile of carotid artery disease. This is so that preventative efforts and early intervention can be targeted on people who are most at risk for the disease. Clinicians evaluate risk using a range of techniques, such as physical examinations, imaging tests, and blood testing. They also consider the patient's family

history, lifestyle choices, and medical history. Clinicians can attempt to reduce the risk of patients who are at high risk by helping them make lifestyle adjustments and receiving medical care. Identification of people who might benefit from surgery or other invasive interventions to prevent stroke requires the use of risk profiling. Utilization of data-driven and machine learning-based models has received more attention in recent years in the enhancement of the risk profile assessment.

Risk profiling for carotid artery disease using data-driven techniques involves using large datasets of patient information to identify patterns and predict the risk of disease in individuals. Machine learning models, such as decision trees and neural networks, are commonly used to analyze these data. These models can consider a wide variety of factors, including demographic information, medical history, lab results, and lifestyle habits. By analyzing these data, the models can identify patterns and predict the risk of carotid artery disease in individuals. This can help to identify individuals at high risk of the disease who may benefit from early intervention and preventative measures. Furthermore, these models can be trained with large data sets, making them more robust and accurate than traditional models. This can help to improve the accuracy and consistency of risk profiling and make it more widely available to medical providers.

Although the identification of people at high risk for carotid artery disease has improved according to current criteria, these guidelines still have several drawbacks. They frequently don't consider the intricate relationships between many risk variables and are based on a small set of risk factors. The rules may not apply to all populations as they are frequently based on observational studies. As a result, evaluating a patient's risk completely may not be possible if only these recommendations are used. To overcome these limitations, more *in-silico* tools are needed. These are computer simulations, computational models, and other types of data analysis that can consider a variety of variables, including genetics and other biomarkers. These techniques can give a patient a more complete picture of their risk, enabling more individualized and successful prevention and treatment efforts. Additionally, these techniques can aid in the discovery of new risk factors and an improved knowledge of disease mechanisms, which can result in the creation of novel therapies and treatments.

Within this work, a cloud - based platform is proposed for clinicians that provides a comprehensive risk assessment for carotid artery disease. It includes three modeling levels: baseline data-driven risk assessment, blood flow simulations and wall shear stress calculations, and plaque progression simulation. The first level of the platform, baseline data-

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driven risk assessment, utilizes machine learning algorithms to analyze large datasets of patient information and identify patterns that can predict the risk of carotid artery disease. This provides a more accurate and comprehensive view of a patient's risk compared to traditional guidelines. The second level, blood flow simulations and wall shear stress calculations, utilizes computational fluid dynamics to simulate blood flow in the carotid artery and calculate the wall shear stress. This allows for a more detailed analysis of the mechanical forces that contribute to plaque buildup and can provide insight into the risk of plaque rupture. The third level, plaque progression simulation, uses computational models to simulate the progression of plaque over time. This allows for the prediction of future plaque growth and the identification of patients at high risk of developing severe disease.

Compared with state-of-the-art similar tools and platforms, the proposed framework is more advanced as it provides a more comprehensive view of a patient's risk and allows for more personalized and effective prevention and treatment strategies. In comparison to existing clinical workflow, TAXINOMISIS is expected to improve the management of asymptomatic patients through a cost-effective strategy. The ultrasound screening recommended by current clinical guidelines is not for asymptomatic patients. TAXINOMISIS offers to clinicians the tools required to selectively screen asymptomatic patients with high-risk scores.

II. STATE OF THE ART

While academia and research centers have worked extensively during the last decade on developing and validating models for risk assessment related to carotid artery disease, there are not many software platforms which materialize such models to actual software components to reach medical workflow (Table 1).

A recent software tool for carotid artery disease management is VASIM [1]. VASIM is a new fully-automated vascular imaging (VASIM) software tool, which was mainly based on the detection of carotid arteries, delineation of the vascular wall, and extraction of the atherosclerotic plaque based on Computed Tomography (CT) imaging modalities. Similar metrics can be extracted with CAROLAB [2] with the main difference that the required imaging modalities are ultrasound images.

CAROTID [3] is one of the first integrated web-based platforms proposed by academia for carotid artery disease management. CAROTID utilizes a multifaceted description of the disease consisting of ultrasound imaging, biochemical and clinical markers aiming at producing an optimal management plan of patients with carotid atherosclerosis. Additionally, Carotid Stenosis Tool [4] explores machine learning algorithms and by using baseline data it produces one and five years risk of ipsilateral ischaemic.

From the applied solutions point of view, mentice© produces software [5] for carotid artery disease management based on CT and ultrasound imaging modalities. Within its services, vessel morphology features and assessment of

stent-wall attachment and local porosity are provided to the end users.

Table 1: State of the art software tools for carotid disease management.

tool	data driven risk models	supported imaging modalities	computational models
VASIM [1]	no	CT	yes (arterial morphology, plaque characterization)
CAROLAB [2]	no	US	yes (arterial morphology, plaque characterization)
CAROTID [3]	yes	US	no
Carotid Stenosis Tool [4]	yes	no	no
mentice© [5]		US/CT	yes (arterial morphology, stent placement)
TAXINOMISIS	yes	US / CT / MRI	yes (arterial morphology, plaque characterization, blood flow, plaque progression,

While the aforementioned approaches cover a wide range of input data and provide the end users useful metrics for better assessment of the disease for a specific patient, they share a common drawback. They are commonly limited to either machine learning approaches or *in-silico* simulations, failing to utilize both techniques. The proposed platform, by exploring the previously described three-level approach, combines both data-driven techniques and *in-silico* simulations, producing finally a complete risk assessment portfolio which facilitates the better understanding of the disease current status and future progression.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed platform has been developed based on the data collected during the clinical study of the TAXINOMIS project [6], [7]. This data has been used to build the relative models and validate them through a set of studies [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15].

The proposed platform is built under the microservices design approach. Microservices is an architectural style that structures an application as a collection of small, independently deployable services. Each service runs a unique process and communicates with other services through a lightweight mechanism, typically an HTTP API. Benefits of using a microservices approach include: (i) scalability: Services can be scaled independently, allowing for more efficient use of resources, (ii) resilience: if one service fails, it does not bring down the entire application, (iii) flexibility: different services can be written in different languages and use different data stores, (iv) ease of deployment: services can be deployed and updated

independently, reducing the risk of application downtime, (v) ease of understanding: A microservices architecture makes it easier to understand and maintain large, complex applications.

Figure 1 presents the platform’s architecture, where all the different modules and microservices are presented.

Figure 1: Detailed architecture of the TAXINOMISIS platform.

More specifically, the platform comprises the following modules: (i) patient electronic folder management, (ii) imaging modalities handling, (iii) 3D arterial reconstruction, using Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Computed Tomography (CT) and / or Ultrasound Imaging (US), (iv) blood flow simulations, (v) plaque evolution simulation and (vi) event risk assessment.

Figure 2 presents the basic functionalities that are made available to the end users through the TAXINOMISIS platform. In detail, through the TAXINOMISIS platform, the clinician can execute the available services to: (i) manage the clinical data, and (ii) run the risk stratification tool. More specifically, according to the upper level of the use-case schema, the data provider can: (i) upload retrospective data, (ii) view and edit the uploaded data, (iii) view useful metadata, (iv) enter prospective data through the electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) system, and (v) upload different types of medical data (e.g., imaging, omics, clinical) for the application of the risk stratification tool. The latter, which is located on the lower level of the use-case schema, provides analytic reports from the modules of the TAXINOMISIS platform architecture (Figure 1) along with the risk stratification which is the result of the application of the TAXINOMISIS modules, including: (i) the 3D reconstruction and plaque characterization, (ii) the agent-based modeling, (iii) the LDL modeling, (iv) the blood flow modeling, (v) the plaque growth modeling, (vi) the plaque rupture modeling, and (vii) the non-imaging stratification analysis. These modules are presented as extensions of the risk stratification level since all these modules are combined together to yield the final risk estimation.

Figure 2: Use cases of the platform’s end user.

Figure 3: Risk assessment screen.

User Interfaces

Within this section, the main screens of the platform are presented and discussed. Figure 3 depicts the risk assessment profile of a specific patient based on non-imaging data. As these risk assessment models have been built based on data-driven techniques, an optional section with Explainable AI analytics (Figure 5) is provided to the end users, to provide a comprehensive insight into the way these specific models function. Next, the patients’ management main screen is provided, which can be used by the clinician to effectively manage his/her patients (Figure 4). Finally, the screen which reports the results of the 3D reconstruction module (Figure 6) and the blood flow simulations (Figure 7).

Figure 4: Patient management panel.

Figure 5: *Explainable AI screen.*

Figure 6: *3D arterial reconstruction results screen.*

IV. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

This manuscript presented a novel *in-silico* platform for patient specific management of the carotid artery disease. Focus was given to the multi-modality 3D reconstruction and plaque characterization tool which is used both by the scientists to evaluate the accuracy and efficacy of the platform and the end-user physicians for case specific simulations. The platform integrates functionalities such as the automatic reconstruction of 3D arterial wall and plaque components, blood flow simulations, plaque evolution simulations and event risk assessment, based both on baseline data and on data derived by the simulations. All the above are implemented in a user - friendly graphical environment on a cloud platform.

Extensive assessment of the platform will follow based on focus groups, aiming to evaluate its usability.

Figure 7: *Blood flow results screen.*

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